

Acknowledgement

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References

1. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
2. *Beilstein* 12, 1229, 524.
3. I. A. SAVICH, V. V. ZELENTSOV and I. SPITSYN, *Vestnik, Moskov. Univ. II, Ser. Mat. Mekh. Astron. Fiz. Khim. No. 1* 233-7 (1956), *Chem. Abstr.* Vol. 53, 1265, (1959).
4. A. SENIER and R. CLARKE, *Beilstein*, 12, I, p. 314, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 99, 2082, 1911.
5. M. S. MAYADEO, A. M. CHAUBAL and S. D. VARTAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 450.

Metal Complexes of N-Phenyl-N'-p-Bromophenyl Thiourea

M. R. CHAURASIA and S. K. SAXENA,

Department of Chemistry, D. A. V. Post-graduate College, Dehradun

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SEVERAL complexes of thioureas have been reported by various workers¹⁻⁶. Very few references⁷⁻¹⁰ have been found with regard to the complexes of unsymmetrical thioureas. Further, certain thiourea derivatives have been found to have analytical¹¹⁻¹³ and biological importance¹⁴⁻¹⁶. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to investigate the metal complexes of N-phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea.

Preparation of Metal complexes :

Ethanolic solution of copper and nickel chloride, bromide, iodide, acetate and nitrate were treated with hot ethanolic solution of N-phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea in 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 ratio

separately and solution refluxed for 50 minutes. The complexes were filtered, washed with a little of ethanol, dry chloroform and dried in vacuo. Their melting points, elemental analysis and magnetic moments are listed in Table 1.

Metal and sulphur in the complexes were estimated by a standard methods. A Coleman Analyser was used for the estimation of nitrogen. Conductance was measured in M/100 dioxane solution using "Toshniwal Conductivity bridge". Infrared spectra in Nujol mulls were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer (Model-720). The magnetic susceptibility was determined by a Faraday Cahn Electrobalance (Model-7550) using mercuric tetrathio-cyanato cobaltate(II) as the standard and using the gram susceptibility values¹⁷. Diamagnetic correction was applied by the use of Pascal's constants.

Results and Discussion

The complexes reported in the present investigation are of the compositions [Cu L X], [Cu L₂ X], [Cu L₃ X] and [Ni L₂ X₂] where X = Cl, Br, I and L = N-phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea. All these complexes are non-electrolytes and the Δ_M values in dioxane solution (M/1000) are very very low. The [Cu L X], [Cu L₂ X], [Cu L₃ X] and [Ni L₂ X₂] complexes are diamagnetic and show sp, sp², sp³ and dsp² types of hybridization.

The infrared spectra of all the complexes of thiourea(L) follow a general pattern and detailed discussion have been recorded. The compounds containing a thioamide moiety have been studied by several workers and it has been suggested that all such compounds give rise to four thioamide bands¹⁸⁻²¹ in their infrared spectra. The four thioamide bands are observed in ligand(L) at 1540, 1250, 1020 and 775 cm⁻¹. The NH absorption bands in the spectrum of thiourea(L) are not shifted to lower wave number on the formation of the metal thiourea complexes indicating that the nitrogen to metal bonds are absent. The sharp band is not observed at 3200 cm⁻¹, is undoubtedly assigned to

TABLE 1—METAL COMPLEXES OF N-PHENYL-N'-p-BROMOPHENYL THIOUREA

Sl. No.	Compound	M.P. (°C)	%M		%N		%S	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	CuL ₂ NO ₃	195	6.98	6.07	9.21	9.36	9.46	9.17
2.	CuLOAc	>250	14.47	14.79	6.20	6.51	7.73	7.44
3.	CuLCl	173	15.53	15.64	6.58	6.89	8.18	7.88
4.	CuL ₂ Cl	141	8.61	8.91	7.63	7.85	9.18	8.97
5.	CuL ₂ Br	98	8.24	8.98	7.08	7.39	8.69	8.44
6.	CuL ₂ I	200	7.59	7.89	6.66	6.96	8.26	7.95
7.	CuL ₂ Cl	198	6.01	6.22	8.01	8.23	9.66	9.41
8.	NiL ₂ Cl ₂	125	7.58	7.89	7.81	7.52	8.46	8.60
9.	NiL ₂ Br ₂	143	6.76	7.05	7.02	6.72	7.53	7.68
10.	NiL ₂ I ₂	130	6.01	6.33	6.34	6.04	6.88	6.91

NOTES

TABLE 2—I. R. DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES OF N-PHENYL-N'-p-BROMOPHENYL THIOUREA

Sl. No.	Compound	ν NH	δ NH	NH ₂ rocking	ν N-C-N (B ₁)	ν N-C=S (1)	ν N-C=S (2)	ν C=S	ν OAc/ ν NO ₂
1.	L	3200m	1600w	1100m	1540s	1250m	1020m	775m	—
2.	CuL ₂ NO ₂	3225m	1605w	1100w	1555m	1230w	1015w	720w	1380s
3.	CuLOAc	3300b 3220b	1640w	1100m	1580w	1200vw	980vw	705vw	1670b
4.	CuLCl	3350vw 3200w	1600w	1115m	1565w	1220vw	1015w	725w	—
5.	CuL ₂ Cl	3250b 3200b	1600w	1105w	1560m	1225w	1015w	740vw	—
6.	CuL ₂ Br	3350w 3200b	1640vw	1100w	1555w	1225vw	1015vw	725vw	—
7.	CuL ₂ I	3350vw 3200m	1600m	1105m	1560m	1220w	1015w	740vw	—
8.	CuL ₂ Cl	3250b 3200b	1605m	1105m	1560m	1235w	1020w	745w	—
9.	NiL ₂ Cl ₂	3200m	1600w	1095m	1550s	1240w	1010w	760w	—
10.	NiL ₂ Br ₂	3210m	1600w	1105m	1545s	1215w	1010w	760m	—
11.	NiL ₂ I ₂	3210m	1600w	1105m	1550m	1240w	1015w	765w	—

Note: w=weak, vw=very weak, m=medium, s=strong b=broad.

the N-H stretching vibration and 1600 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the N-H bending vibration.

In all the complexes examined, there are considerable lowering in the ν N-C=S (1), ν N-C=S (2) and ν C=S bands due to decrease in double bond character of the sulphur to carbon bond and enhanced doubled bond character of the nitrogen to carbon bond. Further, the shift to higher frequency region of the ν N-C-N(B₁) at 1540 cm⁻¹ indicating metal sulphur bonding (see Table 2).

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References

- G. YAGUPSKY, R. H. NEGROTTI and R. LEVITUS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 2603.
- P. C. RATH and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 834.
- P. C. RATH and B. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 710.
- C. PUGLISI and R. LIVITUS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 1069.
- M. M. KHAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 299.
- S. L. HOLT, JR. and R. L. CARLIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 3017.
- D. VENKAPPAYYA and D. H. BROWN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1023.
- M. R. CHAURASIA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1548.
- A. DUTTA AHMED and P. K. MANDAL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 2347.

- B. C. KASHYAP, S. K. BANERJI and A. D. TANEJA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 81.
- R. SOLONIEWCZ, *Chem. Anal. (Warsaw)*, 1964, **9**, 509.
- S. K. SIDHANTA and P. C. KUNDU, *Sci. and Cul.*, 1954, **19**, 506.
- S. K. SIDHANTA and S. N. BANERJI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 53.
- M. H. GOVINDAPPA and J. S. GREWAL, *Indian J. Hert.*, 1965, **22**, 80.
- F. RUSSO, *Bull. Chim. Farm.*, 1961, **100**, 252.
- D. TERFAZ, A. BERECHET, C. CHIRITA and A. VOICU, *Ann. Pharm. Franc.*, 1960, **18**, 37.
- B. N. FIGGIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4190.
- E. LIEBER, C. N. R. RAO, C. N. PILLAI and R. D. HITES, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1958, **36**, 801.
- L. J. BELLAMY, 'The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules' (John Wiley, New York), 1966, p. 54.
- C. N. R. RAO and R. VENKATARAGHAWAN, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1962, **18**, 541.
- C. N. R. RAO, R. VENKATARAGHAWAN and T. R. KASTURI, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 36.

Polarographic Studies of In⁺³ Complexes with Thiodiacetic Acid and Iminodiacetic Acid in Aqueous and Aquo-Non-Aqueous Media

K. M. SUYAN, S. K. SHAH and C. M. GUPTA
Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan,
Jaipur-302 004

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THE dicarboxylic acids having one more coordinating site -N- or -S- atom, other than carboxylic ends have been distinguished as good chelating agents. Various papers¹⁻⁴ have been published on In⁺³ complexes of dicarboxylic acids containing S, N and O atom. In the present communication the